

The literature on the Impact of Working Capital Policy on Profitability: A Comparative Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Adoption of the optimum working capital policy by firms has always been recommended by researcher's world over. However, what is the right working capital policy? The choice between an aggressive, moderate, and liberal working capital policy has not been straightforward. A mixed opinion is seen when we review literature in this regard. This paper carries a structured literature review looking at the 30 recent studies' recommendations on the right policy of working capital. The results have been analysed collectively, and overall findings are presented.

KEYWORDS: Working capital, Working capital policy, Structured literature review.

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite loads of studies in the domain of working capital, the theme stays one of the most loved exploration applicants in the area of finance. Customary exploration has been conveyed in a working capital partner with liquidity, profitability, execution, and so on. What sort of working capital management policy should be adopted – aggressive, moderate, or liberal, has consistently intrigued analysts from finance. Since much research exists on working capital and its implication, the researcher adopted a structured literature review SLR approach for the literature review.

2. THE STRUCTURED LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The settings for the SLR were:

- Zero in on the impact of working capital management practices on MSMEs and different organisations' performance.
- Determination of recent 30 studies on the theme to achieve a sensible size is figured
- Investigation of the examinations is dependent based on like sample, size, and findings of the study.

2.2 Approach for the SLR was as under:

- A mainstream search engine Google Scholar was picked, and search terms utilised were "impact of working capital management practices on profitability."
- To start with, significant ongoing examinations that have been conveyed in the years 2017-2020 were chosen for the review.
- Extra examinations were chosen, moving in reverse into prior years, and determination was halted when the sample size of 30 articles was reached.
- Two explicit viewpoints were examined – does the research uphold a relationship between working capital administration practices and the financial performance of the MSMEs/different organisations? What is the connection found?

Table 1 presents the SLR

Sr. No.	Author (Year)	Country	Sample Size	Relationship (1=Yes, 0=No)	WC policy	Impact On Profitability
1	Daovisan and Shen (2020)	Laos	779	1	Moderate	Positive
2	Rajindra et al (2020)	Indonesia	1752	1	Moderate	Positive
3	Bhattacharyya, & Jagadeesh (2018)	India	12	1	Aggressive	Negative
4	Thakur and Muktedir-Al-Mukit (2017)	Bangladesh	80	1	Aggressive	Negative
5	Lyngstadaas and Berg (2016)	Bangladesh	80	1	Aggressive	Negative
6	Singh et al. (2017)	Global	46	1	Aggressive	Positive
7	Tran et. al	Vietnam	25	1	Aggressive	Positive
8	Afrifa (2016)	UK	160	1	Liberal	Negative
9	Altaf and Shah (2018)	India	437	1	Aggressive	Positive
10	Singhania and Mehta (2017)	Asia	85	1	Moderate	Positive
11	Temtime (2016)	US	176	1	Moderate	Positive
12	Panda & Nanda (2018)	India	1211	1	Aggressive	Positive
13	Adam et al. (2017)	Ghana	6	1	Aggressive	Positive
14	Wichitsathian (2019)	Thailand	41	1	Moderate	Positive
15	Shrivastava et al. (2017)	India	120	1	Liberal	Negative
16	Nobanee (2017)	India	120	1	Liberal	Negative
17	Nguyen et al. (2016)	Vietnam	127	0	NA	NA
18	Tahir and Anuar (2016)	Pakistan	127	1	Aggressive	Positive
19	Geetam and Samanta	India	2	0	NA	NA
20	Ullah et al. (2019)	Bangladesh	10	0	NA	NA
21	Nastiti et al. (2019)	Indonesia	136	1	Moderate	Positive
22	Charitou et al. (2016)	Cyprus	349	1	Moderate	Positive
23	Samiloglu&Akgün (2016)	Turkey	120	1	Aggressive	Positive
24	Jakpar et al (2017)	Malaysia	164	0	NA	NA
25	Usman et al. (2017)	Scandinavian	5194	1	Liberal	Negative
26	Vukovic et al. (2017)	Serbia	95	1	Moderate	Positive
27	Rasyid (2017)	Indonesia	393	1	Aggressive	Positive
28	Baker et al. (2017)	India	110	1	Moderate	Positive
29	Gorondutse et al. (2017)	Malaysia	66	1	Liberal	Negative
30	Ahmed Elbadry (2018)	Egypt	138	1	Aggressive	Positive

3. FINDINGS

Twenty-six out of the 30 studies believed that there is an impact of the firm's working capital policy on profitability. Out of the 26 studies that found an effect, 13 recommended an aggressive approach, 9 recommended a moderate policy, and 4 recommended a liberal policy. Six papers concluded that the working capital policy adopted by the firm harmed profitability. Twenty papers concluded that the working capital policy adopted by the firm had a positive impact on profitability.

4. CONCLUSION

Regular research has been conducted on working capital and its impact on liquidity, profitability, performance, and so forth. Findings from the SLR of 30 studies are a mixed bag. While there is a vast agreement favouring the association between working capital management and financial performance, the impact direction is different. While some studies have favoured an aggressive policy, others have suggested a moderate policy, and still, some others have suggested a liberal policy.

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